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**EFFECTS OF MIX- HOLD- BACK TIME ON THE PROPERTIES OF ORDINARY PORTLAND
CEMENT SANDCRETE BLOCKS**

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Abstract

The study investigated the effects of mix- hold- back time on the properties of ordinary Portland cement sand Crete blocks. Six research questions guided the study. The study employed true experiment design and the sand samples were collected from river Benue in Jimeta Yola North local Government. The brand of cement used was Ashaka cement which was bought in the open market. The batching method used was volume batching, using shovel and gauge. Mix- hold- back time was observed for 40 minutes, 80 minutes and 120 minutes for the three different mix conducted and blocks were produced for each mix category. Compressive strength test, Moisture absorption, and bulk density were conducted on the blocks as specimens in the laboratory. The results of the tests were recorded on tables 1-6. The findings of the study include; the compressive strength of sand Crete blocks at 40 minutes' mix hold back time ranges from 1.66-1.68 N/mm², The rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks produced after 40 minutes mix hold back time ranges from 1.3-1.6 percent. It was recommended that; blocks production should include time keeping as part of block production process to ensure that mix hold back time does not exceed the initial setting time of 30minutes for blocks produced with Ordinary Portland Cement.

Keywords: Effects, Concrete, Cement, Property, Blocks

Introduction

In Nigeria today the use of sand Crete blocks for construction of walls in buildings, has so far played a dominant role as important element. Sand Crete blocks are manufactured using ordinary Portland cement and sand which is mixed with water for workability. The production process and end product minimum requirement are stated by the British Standard Institution for both load bearing and non-load bearing walls. Both load bearing and non-load bearing walls has load to transmit to the foundation of the building; the load bearing walls bears its weight and of other components such as beams, slab, parapets, claddings, roof among others. and transmit to the foundation. The non-load bearing wall carries its weight and transmit same to the foundation of the building. The sizes and requirements for the manufacture of blocks in the building industry are specified by, Nigerian Building Code (NBC), British Standard Institution (BSI), American Standard for Testing Materials (ASTM), National Industrial Standard (NIS).

In standard wet process, mortar for block production is mixed using water for workability, the cement in the mixture begins to react in the presence of water, which is referred to as the setting process, this begins after mixture and is completed at hardening. The mixed mortar is supposed to be used before it begins to set. Mix-hold-back time refers to the period after the initial setting time begins, when the mixing is completed. To avoid the initial setting time to begin, it is

advisable to mix cement and sand thoroughly before adding water and when water is added the final mix is done faster before molding of blocks commences. According to Agrey (2015) mixed mortar is good for use in the first 90minutes after that the setting process has been achieved therefore, it should be discarded because it has started losing some of its important characteristics. This has also been stated by American Society for Testing Materials (ASTM) which stated that concrete should be discarded within 90minutes after mixing. Considering the similarities of concrete and mortar, the same can be applied to avoid losing the required strength.

The mixed mortar forms a cement paste which hydrates, it can also be easily molded into desired shape in its plastic state before it begins to set and harden. Mills (2015) posit that the best time the cement mortar can be molded into any desired shape and the product maintains the required properties is done without disrupting the initial setting time. After the initial setting time the cement paste begins to set. The time at which cement mortar loses its plasticity completely and hardens is called final setting time of cement. At the final setting time it gains its required strength and the chemical reaction in contact with water becomes complete. The initial setting time has important role on the strength of cement. It is therefore important to note that cement mortar has to be placed in position before initial setting time begins in about 20 minutes which shall not be disturbed until setting is complete at final setting time of 600 minutes for ordinary Portland cement. A method of curing is selected to keep the product wet throughout the setting time.

The strength of blocks as defined by Neil and Revindra (2019) is the maximum load it can carry per unit area. The strength of sand Crete blocks are tested through compression and the compressive strength are used commonly in construction industry for the purpose of specification and quality control. Concrete and blocks are brittle materials and the compressive strength of blocks and concrete is the maximum compressive load it can carry per unit area. The maximum strength of blocks and concrete can only be achieved by selective use of materials and maintaining standard mix proportion, compaction methods and curing condition. The standard methods are described in BS 1881 part 116 which requires that the test specimen should be properly cured, and then the loading is done at constant stress after curing process is completed.

The desired properties of sand Crete blocks can be obtained by batching ingredients in certain proportion. Thus, determining the relative amount of materials is known as mix design or proportion. Mix design was defined by Stulze (2019) as the process of selecting and measuring suitable ingredients for mortar to determine their relative quantities and qualities for production of blocks or plaster for certain minimum properties such as; strength, durability, consistency as economically as possible. The purpose of mix design therefore includes; the achievement of the required minimum strength and durability of the product in most economical process. Miller (20014) describes mix proportion provided by the design as a prescribed mix which should be formulae for every similar mortar mix for the entire project. This can further be made easier by the use of standard gauge. The material is selected and batched in such a way that the mortar will have the desired workability while fresh and it could be placed and compacted in the block mold. The fresh mortar for block production should be fluid enough to fill the block mold fully and completed product should develop the required strength and durability at the end of the setting process.

In construction of buildings using cement the aggregate are mixed in a definite proportion, and the reason for having a definite ratio is to ensure that a mix design is selected for a constant and uniform mix for a given project that will give the desired outcome in terms of strength, durability and economy. The important determinant factor for the strength of mortar for block production is the cement to sand ration. To ensure quality of products the mix has to conform to (BS 2028,1970).

Batching of materials is therefore an important Process which was described by John (20014) as a process of storing and measuring out material, which is done in two ways: By volume and by weight. Proportioning by volume is generally adopted except for very large and special work. Measuring by weight may not be very reliable and accurate because it does not often take into consideration that wet sand is saturated with water hence more weight than dry sand. A gauge box is used for proportioning by volume: The gauge box can be made of wood or metal built with its volume related gauge to a bag of cement. The common type of gauge used on site is without bottom, it is placed on the mixing plat form. The aggregate is filled into it and leveled off. It is lifted off and the aggregate spread. The other type of gauge has bottom; when it is filled it is carried by two laborers and tipped into the tilting drum or mix plat form (Stulz, 2019).

Sand Crete blocks are treated through a process known as curing to keep the blocks moist throughout the process; this ensures that sufficient water is made available to the block for a given time to enable it to complete the chemical reactions until it attains the final setting time. According to Jackson and Dhir (20014) the curing process if it is done adequately prevents the rapid loss of moisture through evaporation depending on the weather of the area and curing is done for a period of 3 to 7 days. If the blocks are not adequately cured the rapid rate of evaporation will result to disintegration of the materials. The common method of curing blocks is by sprinkling with water at an interval or morning and evening as condition may warrant. Agrey (2015) specify that mix design of blocks and bricks should be based on the following factors: Types of cement, Size of aggregate, Ratio of mix, the required strength, Quality control, Workability and grade of aggregate.

The outcome of the study will benefit the block production industries as this will draw their attention to prolonged mortar mix-hold-back time that will disrupt the initial setting time of cement there by affecting the properties and general qualities of blocks. This will also help the building industry to improve the quality of blacks produced by observing the mix time to avoid prolonged mix-hold back thereby, reduce the incidences of building failure in the country due to poor quality blocks.

Statement of the Problem

The production of blocks involves the use of sand, and cement which is mixed with water before it is used for molding of blocks. The batching and mix process has to be strictly in accordance with the standard requirement provided by British Standard Institution (BSI 3131, 1974) to enable the product attain the required qualities. After mixing is complete the initial setting time of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) begins until its final setting time and hardens properly. It is expected therefore that before the setting time begins the mixed mortar should be utilized for the production of blocks. The initial setting time has a primary role in the strength of cement and it is mandated that cement paste or mortar is used before it begins the initial setting time within 20 minutes and the process should not be disrupted until it is completed in the final setting time of about 600 minutes. Most of the time due to ignorance the block industries don't emphasize on the importance of setting time of cement so that a large amount of mortar is mixed at a time which will not allow the proper observance of the initial and final setting time of cement. If this practice is allowed to continue the required quality of blocks will continue to be affected and the functional requirement of the walls build with such blocks will not be realized. This study therefore, studied the effects of mix-hold-back time of sand Crete blocks at 40 minute, 80 minutes and 120 minutes and the results are stated in the findings.

Research Questions

1. What is the compressive strength of sand Crete block produced after mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes?
2. What is the compressive strength of sand Crete block produced after mix-hold-back time of 80 minutes?
3. What is the compressive strength of sand Crete block produced after mix-hold-back time of 120 minutes?
4. What is the rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks produced after mix –hold-back time of 40 minutes?
5. What is the rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks produced after mix -hold-back time of 80 minutes?
6. What is the rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks produced after mix-hold-back time of 120 minutes

Methods and Materials

The study employed true experimental design as suggested by Sambo (2008) who wrote that those studies that try to establish cause and effect relationship between variables use true experimental design. The true experiment involves subjecting samples or specimen to experimental conditions in the laboratories for observation and then conducting subsequent tests on the samples or specimen. The experimental procedures which required observation include batching, mixing, molding, compaction, curing, drying, weighing and testing. The study is conducted in Adamawa State, located in North Eastern Nigeria. The sand used for the study in obtained in bank of river Benue in Jimeta, Yola North Local Government area of Adamawa State. The cement used was Ashaka cement brand purchased in the open market. The mix process was conducted manually using shovel and the molding of blocks took place in segments to observe the mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes, 80 minutes, and 120 minutes respectively. The blocks were dried properly before dry density was conducted. The moisture content was determined by calculating the percentage wet weight and dry weight of the blocks.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produce after mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes?

Table 1. Compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produced after Mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes

Specimen	Weight of blocks (KG)	Load at failure (KN)	Compressive Strength N/mm ²	Density Kg/mm ³
1	3.5	12.20	1.67	1974
2	3.2	13.20	1.66	1979
3	3.5	12.21	1.67	1970
4	3.7	13.10	1.68	1970
5	3.6	12.11	1.70	1975

The compressive strength of blocks at mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes’ ranges between 1.66-1,70N/mm³, while the density ranges from 1524-1674Kg/mm². This shows that the compressive strength values of sand Crete blocks meet the BS of 1.44N/mm² minimum requirement for bungalows but not suitable for story buildings. The bulk dry density has fallen within the British Standard for clay bricks which is 1970 Kg/mm³.

Research Question 2

What is the compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produce after mix-hold-back time of 80 minutes?

Table 2. Compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produced after Mix-hold-back time of 80 minutes

Specimen	Weight of blocks (KG)	Load at failure (KN)	Compressive Strength N/mm ²	Density Kg/mm ³
1	3.7	12.11	1.60	1970
2	3.5	13.15	1.50	1968
3	3.6	12.14	1.45	1970
4	3.6	13.13	1.51	1967
5	3.7	12.15	1.52	1970

The compressive strength of blocks on table 2 shows that it ranges from 1.45- 1.60N/mm² while the density of blocks ranges between 1967-1971 Kg/mm². This shows that the strength of blocks is within the requirement of blocks for building bungalows as recommended by the British Standard Institution.

Research Question 3

What is the compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produce after mix-hold-back time of 120 minutes?

Table. Compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produced after Mix-hold-back time of 120 minutes

Specimen	Weight of blocks (Kg)	Load at failure (Kg)	Compressive Strength N/mm ²	Density Kg/mm ³
1	3.6	12.11	1.30	1758
2	3.4	13.01	1.36	1767
3	3.5	12.00	1.40	1767
4	3.4	13.11	1.43	1765
5	3.5	12.00	1.43	1757

Table 3 shows that the compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produced at 120 minutes’ mix-hold-back time ranges from 130-143N/mm². The density ranges from 1757-1767. This shows specimen 1.5 has values lower than that of BS Minimum requirement of 1.44N/mm² recommended for building of bungalows.

Research Question 4

What is the rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks at mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes?

Table 4. Rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks at Mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes

Specimen	Weight of blocks (Kg)	Dry weight (Kg)	Wet weight (Kg)	% Moisture Content
1	3.6	3.5	3.8	0.3
2	3.7	3.6	3.7	0.2
3	3.5	3.6	3.8	0.1
4	3.7	3.6	3.7	0.2
5	3.6	3.7	3.9	0.2

Table 4, shows that moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks at mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes ranges from 0.1-0.3 percent. This indicates that the moisture content is moderate, this was considered in accordance with the BS part 2 : 1998 clause 3.2

Research Question 5

What is the rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks after mix-hold-back time of 80 minutes?

Table 5. Rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks after Mix-hold-back time of 80 minutes

Specimen	Weight of blocks (KG)	Dry weight (Kg)	Wet Weight (Kg)	%Moisture Content
1	3.6	3.5	3.8	0.3
2	3.5	3.5	3.8	0.3
3	3.7	3.5	3.7	0.2
4	3.6	3.4	3.7	0.3
5	3.5	3.5	3.8	0.3

Table 5 shows the result of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks produced at mix-hold-back time of 80 minute. The moisture content values range from 0.2-0.3 percent. This shows increased moisture absorption due to the prolonged mix-hold-back time. This shows that mix-hold-back time of 80 minutes can affect the performance of blocks adversely.

Research Question 6

What is the rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks at mix-hold-back time of 120 minutes?

Table 6. Rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks at Mix-hold-back time of 120 minutes

Specimen	Weight of blocks (Kg)	Dry weight (Kg)	Wet weight (Kg)	%Moisture Content
1	3.6	3.5	3.95	0.45
2	3.5	3.6	3.92	0.42
3	3.5	3.6	3.91	0.31
4	3.6	3.5	3.91	0.41
5	3.5	3.6	3.91	0.31

Table 6. Contains the results of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks produced at 120 minutes mix-hold-back time. The percentage moisture content shows rapid increases which range from 0.31-0.45 percent for specimen 1-5. The increase in moisture content is due to mix-hold-back time of 120 minutes. This means that mix-hold-back eventually will render the cement ineffective in achieving its purpose for strength.

Findings

1. The compressive strength of sand Crete blocks after 40 minutes’ mix-hold-back time ranges from 1.66- 1.68 N/mm². The values are higher than the minimum values of BSI which is 1.44N/mm³ for building bungalows, with this, the expected strength of Portland cement block has been reduced however the compressive strength values shows that the blocks can be used for the construction of bungalows.
2. The compressive strength of sand Crete blocks after 80 minutes’ mix-hold-back time ranges from 1.45 -1.60 N/mm³. The values meet the BS requirement of 1.44N/mm³ for building bungalows.
3. The compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produced after Mix-hold-back time of 120 minutes’ ranges from 1.30-1.43/mm³. This indicates that a mix hold back time of up to two hours has a serious negative effect on the strength and performance of finished Portland cement blocks in constructions.
4. The rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks produced after 40 minutes’ mix-hold-back time ranges from 0.1-0.3 Percent.
5. The rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete blocks produced after 80 minutes’ mix-hold-back time ranges from 0.2-0.3 percent.
6. The rate of moisture absorption of sand Crete block produced after mix-hold-back time 120 minutes’ ranges from 0.31-0.45 percent.

Discussion of Findings

The compressive strength of sand Crete blocks produced after 40 minutes' mix-hold-back time ranges from 1.66-1.68 N/mm³. The minimum sand Crete compressive strength recommended for bungalows by (BSI, 3921, 1974) stands at 1.44N/mm³. This indicates that the mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes has less effect on the strength requirement of sand Crete blocks in accordance with BS minimum recommendations. This further show that when sand Crete blocks are produced at 40 minutes' mix-hold-back times the properties will still be within the range of the minimum requirement of blocks for buildings. This result agrees with Mamu, Baiden and Kerali (2019) who recommended the use of compressive strength of blocks between 1.60-3.5N/mm³ as achieved by their studies for use in building applications. Similarly, the findings also agrees with that of John (2004) who investigated the suitability of commercial available sand Crete blocks in Abuja municipal and had a compressive strength that ranges from 1.69-2.00 N/mm³. The result obtained is slightly higher than that of the current study but both values are within the minimum values recommended for building applications by British Standard Specification.

The compressive strength of blocks at 80minutes mix-hold-back time ranges from 1.45-1.60N/mm³. These values are lower than that obtained at 40 minutes' mix-hold-back time but they are still within the minimum values recommended by BSI for bungalows. Therefore, the strength values of blocks at mix-hold-back time can be used for building of bungalows and non -load bearing walls.

Agrey (2015) had a similar study on the strength of sand Crete blocks in Bauchi State Nigeria. He found that the compressive strength of hollow blocks ranged between 1.55-1.76N/mm³ was adequate for the construction of walls and bungalows as recommended by the British Standard Institution.

The compressive strength of sand Crete blocks at 120 minutes` mix-hold-back time ranges between 1.30-1.43 N/mm³. The values indicate that the mix-hold-back time has very low compressive strength which fall below the BSI recommended minimum value of 1.44N/mm³ for bungalows. Therefore, the mix hold back time of 120 minutes has greater effects on the properties of sand Crete blocks. It is of uttermost importance to observe mix-hold-back time in the production of sand Crete blocks especially in mixing mortar for large works the process can be segmented in a application of water after the dry mix to avoid longer than the necessity mix-hold-back time.

The rates of water absorption at 40 minutes` mix-hold-back time ranges from 0.1-0.3 percent. This indicates moderate moisture absorption at mix-hold-back time of 40 minutes. It also implies that when mortar for sand-crete blocks is mixed and used within 40minutes the rate of moisture absorption will be minimized.

The rate of moisture absorption at 80 minutes' mix-holds-back time ranges from 0.2-0.3 percent. This indicates a high rate of moisture absorption which increases due to the 80 minutes` mix-hold-back time. This further shows that sand Crete blocks produced after mix-hold-back time of up to 80 minutes has increased moisture movement in the pore spaces of the blocks.

The rates of moisture absorption after 120 minutes' mix-hold-back time ranges between 0.31-0.45 percent. The values indicate very high moisture absorption far above that at 40 and 80-minutes' mix hold back time. This shows that production of blocks after mix-hold-back time 120 minutes cannot be used since both the compressive strength and the moisture absorption are below standard.

Conclusion

Block manufacturers begin the process of production of sand Crete blocks by batching of sand and cement which is thoroughly mixed dry before water is added and mixed again into a workable plastic mortar before application. The mixed mortar generates chemical reaction of the cement in the presence of water, cement being a reagent. Cement has Initial and final setting time, the initial setting time begins in 20 minutes after mix is completed and the final setting time last for about 600 minutes. The result of the study shows that mix-hold-back time has effect on the properties of sand Crete blocks. The longer the mix-hold-back time the more adverse effect on the properties of the sand Crete blocks produced.

Recommendations

1. Block manufacturers should include time keeping as part of the block production process to ensure that the mix-hold-back time does not exceed the initial setting time of 20 minutes for ordinary Portland cement.
2. The mix of mortar for block production for large works should be segmented, the dry mix can be made first but wet mix should be segmented to avoid the commencement of initial setting time with the addition of water before the mix is exhausted.

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